

THE APPOLONIA PROJECT

Project background:

The project was a £200million mixed use development over three plots at New Brunswick Conservation Area. A proposed new build, refurbished office spaces, retail and residential buildings. The project consisted multiple buildings which were split into separate job components among four different Architectural firms. The idea of the Client was to ensure diversity of designs on the site, satisfy planning, and local residence requirements. However, such an approach, though clever, made the CDM arrangements quite complicated.

The planning application for the project took two years to obtain due to a rejection of initial project proposal by planning authorities for failing to meet planning requirements. There was a health and safety (H&S) advisor, Lynch, a non-designer, who assisted the Client in the planning application process. When Antonio Architects (who were the Lead Designers and subsequently appointed as Principal Designers [PDs]) were engaged by the Client, the only information made available to them by the Client were some risk assessments on: working at height; slips, trips and falls as well as some site analysis information which were considered vague by the Lead Designers and PDs.

Figure 1: One of the six storey buildings of the Appolonia project

There were six buildings in total at the site. Three of the six buildings were developed by Antonio Architects while the rest of the three were worked on by three different Architectural firms. The choice of Antonio Architects as the Lead Designers and PDs over the entire project resulted from the magnitude of their assigned work, on site, relative to the other three Architectural firms.

The PD's scope of work on site included CDM issues related to underground utilities, road networks, adjacent railway, underground central line underneath the site, and all individual buildings.

The entire development area was zoned into six (6) sites as follows:

- Site S1: Office – 4 to 11 storeys (Existing buildings and warehouses that were retained and handled by Antonio Architects)
- Site S1A: Office – 4 storeys (A Victorian building that was retained, refurbished internally and handled by Spaysis Architects)
- Site S1B: Office – 4 to 5 storeys (A Georgian building that was retained, refurbished internally and handled by Billy Young Architects)
- Site S1C: Office – 4 to 14 storeys (Existing buildings and warehouses that were retained and handled by Antonio Architects)
- Site S2: Office – 4 to 9 storeys (Existing building handled by Sabato Architects)
- Site 3: Existing Loom Court building used for site Project Offices and welfare arrangements

Exhibit 1 indicates the zoned project site with the underground central lines underneath the site.

Client's General H&S Arrangements:

The Client was aware of CDM prior to the project and was assisted by a CDM advisor, H&M Ltd. Due to the complexity of the project, the CDM advisor advised the Client to have a PD lead (i.e. Antonio Architects) who had responsibility over the entire site with specific PDs assigned to individual buildings. Such a support and an advice from the CDM advisor highlights a common arrangement in the construction industry where project Clients when faced with uncertainties regarding the management of H&S risks on projects, often engage the services of other entities (i.e. CDM advisors, PDs, and H&S advisors) – competent in the management of OSH on construction projects – to assist them to fulfill their H&S duties under Regulations.

The specific arrangement had Antonio Architects appointed as the lead PD and they subsequently sub-consulted the PD role for the other individual buildings to the respective Architects working on those buildings. Antonio Architects, thus, provided a common template to all the sub-PDs to deliver their PD information in the same format as Antonio Architects.

Further, due to the nature of the project (a combination of refurbishment and new builds) and the assumed lack of skills regarding temporary works design and façade retention works on the part of the PD, Consar were appointed as Contractors to carry out enabling works such as surveys and temporary works design drawings. They performed an additional PD role, in their

own rights, in support of the lead PD role being handled by Antonio Architects. This phenomenon accentuates one of the approaches to collaborative design H&S risk management (CRM) – partnership – where opportunities for alliancing arrangements could be sought to address capability deficiencies embedded in partnership organisations to handle very complex projects. After the pre-construction stage, Consar continued as sub-contractors, fulfilling a PD role as temporary works designers, under the appointed D&B contractor during the construction phase. A design and build (D&B) approach was employed in the delivery of the project with the PD role transferred to the D&B contractor, Justmoh, upon their appointment. Exhibit 2 indicates the span of the PD and other project participants' responsibilities at the pre-construction stage of the project development process.

A CDM strategy brief was employed on the project as a tool for the management of H&S. Its development started upon the appointment of lead PD and progressed till it was handed over to the D&B contractor when appointed. The deployment of this tool underlines a nascent arrangement (i.e. H&S agenda setting through client brief) by parties upstream of the construction supply chain, particularly the Client with the assistance of the PD, to provide a clear direction and expectation regarding H&S management at the outset of the project. Whereas the conventional Client brief indicates the Client requirements regarding the development of the construction project including aspirations and commitments towards H&S management, the CDM strategy brief identifies and indicates key project H&S risks at an early stage of the project development process. Exhibits 3a – 3b shows an excerpt of the CDM strategy brief identifying significant H&S risks. Although, the process of developing the CDM strategy brief was led by the PD, inputs were often sought from appointed project participants such as Designers. In addition to identifying key H&S risks, the CDM strategy brief also indicated critical project milestones, pre-construction information (PCI) requirements, details of project leadership, procurement strategy, and communication strategy. An excerpt of the CDM strategy brief with these information are is indicated in Exhibits 4a – 4c.

The PD was appointed on a separate contract. Specifically, the Association for Project Safety (APS) contract was used for the PD appointment. The PD services were engaged until the end of stage 4 of RIBA plan of work (technical design). The D&B contractor was appointed at stage 4 and developed the design together with the PD until the expiration of the PD's appointment.

The PD function was largely embedded in the overall design role and therefore difficult to isolate the specific amount of time allocated for the PD services. However, one day per week for purely PD services on the project could be considered a fair estimate of the allocated time for PD services.

Consar was appointed on pre-contract services agreement (PCSA) to provide inputs to the designs at the pre-construction stage. However, due to financial challenges on their part, they pulled out of the project. The project was retendered and a new D&B contractor, Justmoh, was selected.

The lead Designers (i.e. PD) were not involved in the selection of the D&B contractor as the Client considered that process a commercial decision. However, the lead Designers/PD were asked during the selection process to indicate if they had any objections to the D&B contractors which were considered for the projects. The selected D&B contractor was appointed as the Principal Contractor by the Client.

The allowance for the PD services on the project was based on a percentage of the contract sum, an approach which corroborates one of the four main categories of compensations regarding PD services (i.e. time-based, lump sum, percentage of project cost, and task-based) in the UK construction industry. The percentage value was about 0.08% and was mostly informed by the complexity of the project and the magnitude of the contract sum. Highly complex projects attracted higher percentage values and vice versa. Similarly, higher contract sums also attracted lower percentage values and vice versa. The sub-PDs indicated their PD services fees to the lead PD and were paid from the overall PD fee charged by the lead PD. The other Designers also made allowances for their CDM duties on the project. However, these were embedded in their overall professional fees.

The assembling of project dutyholders and their attendant competences with focus on H&S were managed by the Client's CDM advisor on behalf of the Client. The dutyholders evidenced H&S competence through the Safety Schemes in Procurement (SSIP) framework. Further, the Client advisors also prioritised the specific skills, knowledge and experiences (SKE) of the individual dutyholders in respect of the complexity of the project. As a result, dutyholders were made to complete standard pre-qualification questionnaire in addition to the SSIP competence assessment. Additionally, the CVs of the prospective dutyholders were perused for specific SKE in the light of the project under consideration. The assistance offered by the CDM advisor to the Client concerning getting the right people to the project highlights a pervasive arrangement (i.e. reliance on prior appointees already assessed for skills, knowledge, experience [SKE]) regarding assembling the project supply chain with focus on H&S in the UK construction industry. Exhibits 5 and 6 indicate the standard pre-qualification questionnaire for the Designers and PC, respectively. The H&S arrangements were considered appropriate for the project.

Organisation:

There was no specific organogram for the way H&S was organised on the project. The organisation, particularly from a human resource perspective, followed the traditional arrangement where dutyholders were appointed to fulfil their traditional roles on projects. The project team consisted:

- Project manager
- Principal Designer (same as lead Designers and Architects)
- Principal Contractor (same as D&B contractor)
- Architects
- Facilities Manager
- Landscape Architects
- Cost Consultants
- Structural Engineers
- Services Engineers
- Fire Engineers
- Façade Consultants
- Transport Consultants (the development area was located at a heavy transportation network area)

- Planning Consultants
- Security Consultants (the development was situated at a very difficult and high security area)
- Sustainability Consultants
- Access Consultants
- Party wall Surveyors
- Approved Inspector
- Acoustic Consultants
- Demolition Consultants/Enabling Works Contractors
- Construction Contractors (advised on construction methods)
- Legal Consultants
- Archaeology Consultants (the development area had some features dating back to the roman empire era)
- Timber Specialists (the buildings had some rotten timber members from the Victorian era and an advice required as to what members to retain and remove).
- Fabric Specialists (the conditions of the existing buildings needed to be established before demolishing or retaining them)

A directory document indicating the major professional services, the entities involved, and contact details was used as one-stop information point regarding all project participants. This information related to entities who were responsible, accountable, might be consulted, and informed regarding certain aspects and risks related to the project. Exhibit 7 indicates the directory of project participants.

Principal CDM Documents Preparation:

Key CDM documents were developed on the project. These included the pre-construction information (PCI), construction phase plan (CPP) and H&S File (HSF). The preparation of the PCI started prior to the appointment of the lead Designers/PD. However, the information were quite scanty and vague. Systematic and proper development of the PCI started when the PD was appointed. They provided further details to the available PCI and also pulled all of them into a CDM strategy brief toolkit for easy access and usage by all relevant dutyholders.

Since the project was a D&B one, the scope of the PD's work as agreed with the Client, at the pre-construction stage, mainly entailed highlighting the H&S risks on the project site for the attention and management by the D&B contractor. Further, it included documenting and indicating design decisions prior to the appointment of the D&B contractor having regard to the H&S risks associated with the project development.

The PD developed a site investigation and survey data tracker to manage the PCI on the project. The tracker indicated information pertaining to the required PCI, the dutyholder responsible for the PCI and the status – whether the PCI is awaiting or obtained. Exhibits 8a – 8b indicates the site investigation and survey data tracker for the management of project PCI.

Additionally, a CDM site analysis map, as part of the CDM strategy brief toolkit, was developed by the PD to indicate the key CDM issues and the existing site constraints.

The identified H&S risks on the site were subsequently transferred to a Hazard Awareness and Risk Management Register (HARMR) for detailed description of the risks with indication of measures to manage them. Exhibits 9a – 9c indicates an excerpt of the HARMR. The identified H&S risks on the site, and their resultant information, constituted a significant share of the pre-construction information and these included:

- Scheduled Ancient Monument (SAM) information (which indicated risks of archaeological finds)
- Conservation area information
- Information on statutory listed buildings and road surfaces
- Information on locally listed buildings
- Risk of collapse of existing buildings
- Asbestos survey
- Exposure to toxic materials, e.g. lead paint
- Adjacent buildings – party walls
- Live network rail (NR) line
- Network rail retaining wall
- Proximity of London Underground (LU) Central line tunnels
- Piling adjacent to LU tunnels and NR line
- Public sewers and diversions
- Working adjacent to live services
- Existing UKPN substation relocation
- Ground obstructions
- Deep basement/land contamination
- Unexploded ordnance (UXO)
- Ground gas
- Excessive noise, dust and vibration
- Surveys, reports and investigation (which included structural and timber fabric surveys and CCTV surveys for site drainage complete)
- Fibre optic cables
- Surrounding highways
- Site access and establishment

The preparation of the Construction Phase Plan (CPP) started at RIBA stage 4 (technical design) where the D&B contractor, who doubled as the PC, was appointed. The lead PD supplied all relevant PCI information to the PC and further provided explanations to any PCI that was not easily understandable to the PC during interactions at the technical design stage. The adequacy of the CPP was checked and approved on behalf of the Client by the Client advisor upon its completion. The CDM Regulations 2015 is not quite clear on the dutyholder responsible for reviewing the quality of the CPP. Hence, its review by the CDM advisor – an exercise also often carried out by the PD – is deemed to be a Client expectation as no express duty is placed on any project participant in this way.

The preparation of the Health and Safety File (HSF) started from the development of the CDM strategy brief document. The PD provided a broad framework indicating: the information requirement; dutyholder responsible for the information; and the status of the information –

whether completed or still required – in respect of the HSF preparation. Exhibit 10 shows the broad HSF information framework. The overarching framework regarding HSF information was augmented by the PD's supply of detailed HSF template to be completed by all relevant dutyholders as part of the process of preparing the File. This template is indicated in Exhibit 11. The HSF was handed over to the PC at the end of stage 4 when the engagement of the lead PD was ended. The PC was required to update it during the construction phase and hand it over to the Client together with operations and maintenance (O&M) manuals, as-built drawings as well as any other information prescribed by the Client advisor.

The main challenge regarding the preparation of the principal CDM documents was the difficulty, initially, in getting the sub-PDs to agree and adopt the format proposed by the lead PDs in documents compilations. Each sub-PD was comfortable in supplying information in their own format. This phenomenon of unharmonised templates for exchanges of H&S information across organisations along the project supply chain is endemic to the preparation of the principal CDM documents. It often leads to tensions among project participants and eventually undermines the quality of the documents prepared.

Coordination:

Coordination of the inputs by the different dutyholders was managed by a centralised repository platform which was set up by the Client. This is one of the commonest communication methods in the construction industry among project participants and often set up on large projects. The advantage with this arrangement is information visibility and centrality which is made possible by the proliferation of cloud-based document storage and sharing platforms.

Further coordination of dutyholders' efforts were handled by meetings. There were monthly design team meetings, where H&S issues were discussed with other project attributes such as sustainability, structures, archaeology, among others. Exhibit 12 indicates an excerpt of the agenda of a design team meeting. Progress meetings, monthly, were also held at the pre-construction stage to inform the Client of developments on the project. Considering the degree of complexity of the project, weekly CDM review workshops were organised to address all H&S challenges associated with the design. At workshops, significant individual and multi-factorial hazards are highlighted for effective management. Big-ticket risks were often prioritised at workshops for attention. Overtime, they were moved from red-labelled risks to green or amber-labelled risks as a result of being designed-out or effective mitigation measures proffered, respectively. Exhibits 11a – 11c shows an excerpt of the HARMR indicating risk statuses and owners required to manage them.

Again, the level of complexity of the project made it impracticable to have one PD to coordinate all CDM issues on the project. Hence, there were sub-PDs responsible for specific projects and sites with a lead PD who oversaw and coordinated all CDM issues among them. A similar arrangement was reported by Webster¹ on the London 2012 Olympics construction programme where there were multiple CDM-Cs with a CDM integrator having an oversight function for all of them.

¹ Webster, M. (2013). The use of CDM (2007) in the London 2012 construction programme. Proceedings of the Institute of Civil Engineering, 166, 35–41. doi:10.1680/cien.12.00010

There were a lot of engagements and coordination between the PD, Designers and the PC, particularly at the pre-construction stage. These sometimes took all-day meetings and resulted from the decision of the PC to opt for offsite pre-cast brick panels as opposed to initially designed and specified onsite brick construction. The allowance of such critical and frequent meetings on the project by the Client highlights the Client's quality leadership arrangements as opposed to instances where such poor leadership arrangements by some Clients (underpinned by cost reduction agenda through value engineering) often undermine the quality of H&S arrangements on projects, a phenomenon common with D&B projects. Figure 2 shows an elevation with the offsite pre-cast brick panel façade.

Regarding the coordination between Designers and the PC on temporary works design, the lead Designers and PD only specified what building features (i.e. slab, façade, basement, etc) needed to be retained or demolished, in scoping drawings. Subsequently, the PD for enabling and temporary works with the support of the Structural Engineers planned and carried out the retention and demolition works.

Though there were programmed meetings on the project, they were adapted to allow for some ad hoc meetings to address issues that required urgent attention as to when they arose. The complexity of the project and the number of dutyholders involved meant that meetings attendees were drawn on need-to-know basis to ensure effectiveness of meetings. This arrangement also freed resources to attend to other productive work on the project.

The lead Designers (PD) convened and coordinated meetings at the pre-construction stage, took the minutes of meetings and subsequently updated the CDM strategy brief toolkit with relevant information from the minutes. The centralised documentation of H&S issues via the CDM strategy brief ensured a united purpose among all dutyholders regarding OSH risk management on the project.

PROJECT	APPOLONIA PROJECT		WORK STAGE	4	REVISION & DATE	P03	14.06.2018
AREA, ELEMENT OR SIGNIFICANT RISK ISSUE	BUILDING FORM, MATERIAL, ACTIVITY, LOCATION HAZARDS (Identified)	ELIMINATE or AVOID risks (So far as reasonably practicable) During early design stages	REDUCE risks (As low as reasonably practicable) Safe systems & work protection	INFORMATION to be provided with design eg. Specialist Design & Client input	DESIGN CONTROL METHODS Dates, comments, guidance etc.	RISK Tolerable Ongoing Action Needed	

<p>S1a-2.10 Weight of Building Materials and Elements</p> <p>S1a-2.12 Large Format Sheet Material</p>		<p>The facade contains large elements constructed with precast concrete. Sizes and the weights to be calculated and suitable lifting equipment be provided.</p> <p>Floor to ceiling heights throughout the building range from 2.1m - 3.2m. Internal partitions walls will require large sheets of plasterboard.</p>	Note
		<p>ACTIONS:</p> <p>A. Specialist precast supplier and contractor to review Facade Engineer's and MCO's Stage 4a information and comment on design and logistics.</p>	EOC/PC
		<p>B. Contractor to comment on buildability and construction sequence for installation of windows.</p>	EOC/PC
		<p>C. Plasterboard could be specified in half sheet sizes.</p>	PC

Figure 2: An elevation with the offsite pre-cast brick panel façade

Conclusions and lessons:

As the economy grows, it presents a lot of opportunities to investors and Clients in the real estate sector. However, the need to keep a balance between economic opportunities and conservation often leads to very complex projects as in the case of Appolonia project. Such complex projects may have implications for H&S management. The complexities introduced would, thus, require unconventional CDM arrangements to ensure optimal OSH performance on projects.

Project team meetings and early contractor involvement (ECI) are considered to be two useful collaborative risk management approaches on very large and complex projects. This case presents a number of useful lessons that may benefit future projects regarding H&S risks management and these include the following:

- The use of a CDM strategy brief toolkit, which was a blend of pictures and narrations, instead of a normal spreadsheet was an effective approach to communicating and managing H&S risks on the project. This tool brought project H&S risks alive and prompted pragmatic solutions from project participants to address them.
- Even though the Regulations suggest one PD for a project, the level of complexity of the project necessitated a hierarchy of PDs, in the effective coordination of H&S. The current Regulations do not clearly indicate provisions for such a nature of configuration. Therefore, promoters of future projects must always consider the express provisions in the Regulations, regarding H&S arrangements, as minimum requirements and think outside of the box in the light of ever increasing project complexity to ensure desirable H&S outcomes on projects.
- On very complex projects, particularly those involving a mix of demolition, refurbishment and new builds, pragmatism required the appointment of a parallel PD in addition the conventional PD to handle a specialised aspect of the project beyond the capability of the conventional PD, particularly at the pre-construction stage. Hence, partnerships that seek opportunities to dovetail the competences of project participants, for optimal H&S performance on projects, should be encouraged by project Clients.

EXHIBITS

Exhibit 1: The zoned project site with underground central line underneath the site

Exhibit 2: The span of PD and other project participants' responsibilities at the pre-construction stage

Rev: 14/06/2018		Appolonia Project: Principal Designer Interface Responsibilities.																												
Site	Principal Designer	Description	2017												2018												2019			
			Q3			Q4			Q1			Q2			Q3			Q4			Q1		Q2		Q3		Q4			
			Jul	Aug	Sep	Oct	Nov	Dec	Jan	Feb	Mar	Apr	May	Jun	Jul	Aug	Sep	Oct	Nov	Dec	Jan	Feb	Mar	Apr	May	Jun	Jul	Aug	Sep	Oct
			← Phase 1 →												← Phase 2 →												← Phase 3 →			
All Phases / sites	H&M Ltd	Client Adviser	H&M Ltd PD Overview. Client Advisory Role for Duration of Development																											
Sub Structure																														
S1, S1a, S1b, S1c, S2, S3, Public Realm	Consar	Enabling works Contract. Contract Works and CDP	Consar PD for Enabling Works (Ground level and below)																											
All	Lead Designer	Design Development	Architect Lead Designers interface with Consar for any changes to Sub Structure																											
Super Structure (above Ground level)																														
S1, S1a, S1b, S1c, S3, Public Realm	Antonio Arch.	Super Structure works (above ground)	Antonio Architects PD for Design Development																											
S2	Sabato Arch.	Super Structure works (above ground)	Sabato Architects PD for Design Development S2																											
		Justmoh Contract date 10th June	♦																											
All Phases/ sites	Justmoh	All Design and Contract works.	Justmoh Project PD																											
Phase 1: Lead Designers are PD																														
Phase 2:			<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Consar PD for Enabling works (up to Ground Level). - Lead Designers PD above ground level (superstructure) for respective buildings. 																											
Phase 3: Justmoh PD for project																														

Exhibit 3a: An excerpt of the CDM strategy brief identifying significant H&S risks

Significant Risk/ Issue No.	Significant CDM Issues/ Description of Significant Risk * Generic issues to be avoided	Mitigation, Control Measures or further information 'So far as in reasonably practicable' (SFARP)	Design Issues Owner & Status Not tolerable ■ Ongoing ■ Tolerable ■	H&S file ✓
1.0	Site Environs and Site Establishment Strategy (incl. local features, transport corridors, pedestrian flow, welfare provisions, vehicular access, site storage, unloading, crange etc)			
			Action Owner	✓
2.0	Site Enabling Strategy (incl. demolitions, de-contamination, remediation, temp. works etc.)			✓
3.0	Existing Building and Services Strategy (incl. above and below ground features, adjoining properties, party wall issues etc)			
4.0	Structural Works Strategy (incl. permanent, temporary & demolition requirements)			
5.0	Heavy Component Movement Strategy (incl. large, heavy and awkward components, method of vertical and horizontal movement for delivery storage & placement)			
6.0	Off-site & On-site manufacturing and assembly strategy (incl. prefabricated, modular, hand installed etc)			

* **Significant risks** not necessarily those that involve the greatest risks, but those (including health risks) that are not likely to be obvious, are unusual, or likely to be difficult to manage effectively (Ref. CDM 2015 L153).

Exhibit 3b: An excerpt of the CDM strategy brief identifying significant H&S risks

Significant Risk/ Issue No.	Significant CDM Issues/ Description of Significant Risk* Generic issues to be avoided	Mitigation, Control Measures or further information 'So far as in reasonably practicable' (SFARP)	Design Issues Owner & Status Not tolerable	H&S file ✓
7.0	Safe working at height strategies (e.g. significant roof access, high ceilings, etc.)			
8.0	Health Strategy (eg: excessive, dust, MSD, HAV, noise minimisation etc.)			
9.0	Plant & Services design and installation strategy (e.g. location and construction issues)			
10.0	Plant Replacement strategy (e.g. future access issues)			
11.0	Plant, plantrooms services + riser access and Maintenance strategy			
12.0	Facade access, window cleaning and glass replacement strategy			
13.0	Phasing strategy (e.g. site, construction, occupation, etc.)			
14.0	Miscellaneous issues (e.g. landscaping, wellbeing, Workplace Regulations etc.)			

* **Significant risks** not necessarily those that involve the greatest risks, but those (including health risks) that are not likely to be obvious, are unusual, or likely to be difficult to manage effectively (Ref. CDM 2015 L153).

Exhibit 4a: An excerpt of the CDM strategy brief indicating key project information

Project Name	Appolonia Project	Project Number	40833
Building Type (new construction, refurbishment, asset management, decommissioning)	New and refurbished existing buildings	Date of Review	14.06.2018
Design Stage	Stage 4	Revision no	P03

Guidance Note: To be discussed with client and completed by the Project Architect at the earliest stage of the project and updated at each RIBA work-stage if changes occur.

CDM STRATEGY BRIEF	PROJECT LEADER RESPONSES	CONTACT Nos, COMMENTS, NOTES, DATES, ETC
Project Details		
Description of Project - Outline scope of works	Mixed use development over three plots in New Brunswick Conservation Area. Proposed new build and refurbished office space, retail and residential buildings. Antonio Architects responsible for Plots S1 (including 12-13 Pink Street), S1c and S3 (S3 excluded from this report). Spaysis Architects and Billy Young Architects appointed to end of Stage D as sub consultants to Antonio Architects on S1a and S1b respectively. Sabato Architects working on Site S2, appointed directly to Springfield Investment.	Feasibility scheme completed December 2014 and stage C/ planning submission completed 19/12/14 with planning submission. Rejected at LBTH Planning Committee June/July 2015, GLA call in September 2015 with revisions requested to incorporate 12-13 Pink Street Warehouses. GLA granted permission on 14th January 2016. Judicial Review into decision to call scheme in by GLA due March 2016.
Address/location/environment of site	Pink Street	
Client Brief / Outline Scope of Work		
Operational requirements (any existing activities to remain eg. Occupation, etc.)	Vacant possession required prior to commencement on site.	
H&S expectations of client (if above Statutory requirements)	None advised.	Client to confirm if any client rules, etc.
H&S file -format & index (if different to Appendix 4 L153)	Arcadis issued format for H&S file info on 15 March 2019.	
Project Timescales (what are the key stages and how long will they run for?)		
RIBA Stage AB: Preparation and Brief	Completed - 10 Jan 2014	
RIBA Stage C: Concept Design	Completed - 31 Dec 2015	Stage C completed with planning
RIBA Stage D: Developed Design	Completed - 15 Jun 2017	Original stage D deadline 06 2015, planning delay and GLA call in resulted in redesign of 12-13 Pink Street on S1, with submission of Stage D in April 2016. Stage D sign off awaited from BL. Appointed to undertake a Stage D 'Refresh' - updating the scheme to deal with new Building Regulations and adding in items not completed/incorporated at the end of the previous Stage D.
RIBA Stage 3: Developed Design	Completed - 30 Nov 2017	

Exhibit 4b: An excerpt of the CDM strategy brief indicating key project information

Project Name	Appolonia Project	Project Number	40833
Building Type (new construction, refurbishment, asset management, decommissioning)	New and refurbished existing buildings	Date of Review	14.06.2018
Design Stage	Stage 4	Revision no	P03

CDM STRATEGY BRIEF	PROJECT LEADER RESPONSES	CONTACT Nos, COMMENTS, NOTES, DATES, ETC
RIBA Stage 4: Technical Design	Completed - 29 April 2019	
Fit out of Loom Court for Site Welfare	Completed	Antonio Architects temporary PD role
RIBA Stage 5: Construction	S1 Aug 22 / S1A Feb 22 / S1B Jun 22 / S1C Jun 22 - subject to new contractor review	
RIBA Stage 6: Handover and Close Out	TBA	
Clarify at which of the above stages are you starting the CDM/Principal Designer process	Taking over from Stace at Stage D refresh - February 2018.	
Is there any pre-existing CDM Analysis, risk register or relevant information & where?	Yes - Lynch as the H&S adviser at the previous stage submitted Hazard Elimination & Management Register Rev A on 16 April 2016.	Stace LLP continued in the role of CDM Coordinator until end of the transition period (5th October 2015)
Strategic Risks (what are the significant or unusual H&S risks?)		
Work involving Particular Risks - Refer to L153 Schedule 3	Strip out and protection/removal of asbestos/lead contamination Demolition of existing buildings with façade retention Live railway line to the north elevation The CDM HARM Register and Analysis & Options Matrix highlight the key particular risks.	
Strategic Design Intent and associated risks (e.g. Major temporary works) (e.g. Stability considerations) (e.g. Unusual site constraints and logistics)	Strip out, demolition, façade retention Railway line - retaining wall Red route on Penn High Street & Commercial Street Refer also to CDM HARM Register and Analysis & Options Matrix. Will be updated regularly.	
Pre-construction information requirements		
Pre-Construction Information - See Appendix 2 in L153 - Surveys, Constraints, Planning conditions, etc		
Additional requirements for this specific Construction site - Check L153 Part 4 for General Requirements		

Exhibit 4c: An excerpt of the CDM strategy brief indicating key project information

Project Name	Appolonia Project	Project Number	40833
Building Type (new construction, refurbishment, asset management, decommissioning)	New and refurbished existing buildings	Date of Review	14.06.2018
Design Stage	Stage 4	Revision no	P03

CDM STRATEGY BRIEF	PROJECT LEADER RESPONSES	CONTACT Nos, COMMENTS, NOTES, DATES, ETC
Project Leadership		
Client - lead contact and organisation	Springfield Investment - Daniel Mantey	
Project Manager	P&M Consult - Evelyn Short	
Principal designer - lead contact and organisation	Antonio Architects - Patrick Kirk (CDM Lead)	
Principal contractor - lead contact and organisation	Enabling works: Consar - Ben Long Construction: TBC	
Design Team - lead contact and organisation	Antonio Architects Lead consultant (with sub-consultants) - Refer to Appendix A Directory List	
Procurement strategy		
Contract Sum/Anticipated Project Cost	Nom £200,000,000	
Form of Contract	Design and Build	
Communication strategy		
Team meetings anticipated, Number, frequency, length, location etc. at each work stage.	Monthly Design Team Meeting & Progress Meeting Weekly CDM Review Workshops	PD updates are to be included on Monthly Reports.
Induction process - for new team members	This document serves the design induction process.	
Visual tools, drawings, analysis documents	Revit and CAD drawings with CDM issues annotated by visual symbols in this document.	
Use of BIM	Yes	
Health and Safety File	No	

Exhibit 5: A sample of standard questionnaire for Designers' organisational capability assessment

1 Company Details	Response/Comment
1.1 Company Name:	
1.2 Head Office (Registered Office):	
1.3 Correspondence address (if different to above):	
1.4 Date trading commenced:	
1.5 Type of Company (Limited, partnership sole trader, etc.):	
1.6 Contact Details:	
2 Types of Service(s) Provided	
2.1 Services Provided:	
2.2 Please provide details of similar projects undertaken by yourselves:	
3 Health & Safety (H&S) Policy	
3.1 Please provide a copy of your current general H&S policy statement:	
3.2 Please provide a copy of your management organisation chart highlighting those with H&S responsibilities:	
3.3 Please provide details of your company management system, in particular your H&S management system and other arrangements for putting the H&S policy into effect:	
4 Insurance	
4.1 Please provide a copy of your insurance certificate that applies to the work you perform or intend to perform for..... (e.g. Employers Liability, Public Liability, Contractors All Risks, Construction Plant and Professional Indemnity):	
4.2 Has your Insurer made any conditions on your policy within the last 3 years? (If so, please provide details):	
Construction (Design and Management) Regulations 2015 (CDM 2015)	
5.1 Please confirm you understand the requirements of Regulation 8 of the CDM 2015 and explain how your organisation meets them.	

5.2 Please confirm you understand the requirements of Regulations 9 and 10 of the CDM 2015 and explain how your organisation meets them.	
5.3 Please confirm you understand the general principles of prevention. Please give examples of how you achieve these during your works.	
5.4 Please provide details on how your organisation deals with foreseeable risks to the health or safety of any persons – (a) Carrying out or liable to be affected by construction work (b) Maintaining or cleaning a structure (c) Using a structure as a workplace	
5.5 Please provide details on how you communicate to other parties such as the Client, Principal Designer, Principal Contractor and other Designers to provide them with information about the design, construction or maintenance of structures.	
6 Health and Safety Resources	
6.1 Please provide relevant H&S certification for the members of staff involved in these types of project:	
6.2 Please provide the names and qualifications of internal H&S advisors and/external H&S consultants used by your organisation:	
6.3 Please outline any specialist resources which are utilised by your organisation in an advisory capacity in H&S:	
6.4 Please describe how each member of the team is communicated with, so that they are aware of his/her responsibilities under the CDM 2015.	
7 Training and Information	
7.1 Please provide details of Designers H&S training, in particular training focusing on health and safety in design.	
7.2 Please provide details of your CPD programme.	
7.3 Please provide details of key project personnel [Names, CV's, qualifications, memberships etc]	
7.4 Please provide evidence of the Designers experience with similar projects.	
7.5 Provide brief details of similar design projects undertaken [locations, description, dates, size and cost]	

7.6 Provide references from those who have engaged the Designers on similar projects	
8 Resources and Workforce Involvement	
8.1 Please outline how you allocate sufficient time and resources when planning and delivering projects you are engaged in	
8.2 Please provide details of the number of competent personnel available to work on the projects	
8.3 Please provide details of design and technical support facilities [e.g. computing, health and safety guidance, specialist technical links with external experts etc]	
8.4 Please provide evidence of health and safety consultation with the workforce [names of safety representatives, records of health and safety meetings/committees etc]	
9 Monitoring, Audit and Review	
9.1 Please provide details of the monitoring, audit and review procedures for your H&S systems. Including evidence of any audits that the management responses.	
10 Hazard Elimination and Risk Control	
10.1 Please Provide details on how you ensure co-operation with the design team, other designers, contractors and the Principal Designer.	
10.2 Please provide details on how hazards are eliminated and any remaining risks are controlled including examples of your design risk assessment system.	
10.3 Please provide examples of how risks have been reduced by your designs.	
10.4 Please provide confirmation that any structure used as a workplace will meet the requirements of the Workplace [Health Safety and Welfare] Regulations 1992. Please provide examples on how this has been achieved on projects you have carried out.	
10.5 Please provide details on how you will provide adequate information with your designs and information needed for the health and safety file.	

11 Sub-Contracting/Consulting Procedures	
11.1 Please provide evidence showing how you ensure sub-contractors/consultants have sufficient skills, knowledge and experience to undertake their works for yourselves	
11.2 Will you be engaging or commission other persons to carry out designs on your behalf for this project [If so, please provide details of them and how you monitor their activities]:	
12 Accident Reporting, Enforcement and Investigation	
12.1 Please provide details on how you record and investigate accidents.	
12.2 Please provide details of any intervention or enforcement action taken over the last 5 years and actions taken to prevent recurrence.	
Further information	
Please provide any further information which you think will assist in assessing your skills, knowledge, experience and organisational capability.	

We undertake to provide the designated designer adequate time and technical support facilities to fulfil the requirements under Regulations 8, 9 and 10 of the

Construction (Design and Management) Regulations 2015.

Signed:

On behalf of (Company Name):

Date:

Signed:

.....

Date:

.....

**Director/Partner Responsible for Health &
Safety**

Exhibit 6: A sample of standard questionnaire for Principal Contractor’s organisational capability assessment

Questionnaire Checklist	Response/Comment
1 Health and Safety Policy	
1.1 Provide a copy of your Health and Safety Policy Statement.	
1.2 Provide a copy of your management organisation chart, complete with details of the health and safety team.	
2 Arrangements	
2.1 Provide details of your company Management System, in particular your Health and Safety Management System and any other arrangements for putting the Health and Safety Policy into effect.	
3 Competent Advice	
3.1 Please provide the name and competency details of your source of health and safety advice.	
4 Training and Information	
4.1 Provide details of a Health and Safety training culture to include records, certificates and adequate H&S induction training for site based personnel.	
4.2 Provide details of an active CPD programme.	
5 Individual Qualifications and Experience	
5.1 Provide details (names and CV’s) of key project personnel identifying their skills, knowledge, experience and training to carry out and manage the works.	
5.2 Provide evidence of experience with similar projects for project personnel.	
5.3 Give brief details of similar projects undertaken (locations, description, dates, size and cost) by the company. Include a reference contact for previous Clients.	
6 Monitoring, audit and review	

6.1 Provide details of the monitoring, audit and review procedures for your health and safety systems. Include evidence of any audits and the management responses.	
7 Resources and workforce involvement	
7.1 Give details on the number of competent personnel available to work on the project.	
7.2 Provide details of the technical resources available to assist project personnel in the implementation of the project. (e.g. computing, health and safety guidance, specialist technical links with external experts etc.)	
7.3 Provide evidence of health and safety consultation with workforce (names of safety representatives, records of health and safety meetings/committees etc).	
8 Accident reporting, enforcement & investigation	
8.1 Give details on the way in which you record and investigate accidents and incidents, giving details of the last 2 accidents and actions taken to prevent recurrence.	
8.2 Provide details of any enforcement action taken over the last 5 years and actions taken to put matters right.	
8.3 Provide details of your accident statistics for the last 3 years and their basis.	
9 Sub-contracting, consulting procedures	
9.1 Provide evidence showing how you ensure sub-contractors/consultants are competent.	
9.2 Give details showing how you monitor the performance of subcontractors.	
10 Risk assessment	
10.1 Provide evidence showing how the company will identify significant H&S risks and how they will be controlled.	
10.2 Provide samples of risk assessments/safe systems of work/method statements.	

11 Co-operation and co-ordination	
11.1 Provide evidence of how the company co-ordinates its work with others.	
12 Further information	
12.1 Provide any further information which you think will help assess your competence and resources	

Exhibit 7: Directory of project participants

Project participant	Organisation	Contact	Ref
Client	Springfield Investment 82 Falcon street WV1 5NH, Penn	Seth Blay Tel: 000000000 J.Mills@precosh.com	Client
Project Manager	P&M Consult 47 Macron street 7DT 4JK, Daren	Evelyn Shane Tel: 000000000 E.Shane@precosh.com	P&M
CDM Advisor	H&M Ltd 50 Palton street TY1 5BV, Surrey	Victor Seldon Tel: 000000000 V.Seldon@precosh.com	H&M
Lead Architects	Antonio Architects 5 Mansperger Street 3KL 5GH, Beverly	Bradley Jones Tel: 000000000 B.Jones@precosh.com	AA
Project Architects 1	Spaysis Architects 20 Old Street HN2 8WH, Benson	Stanley Mauer Tel: 000000000 S.Mauer@precosh.com	SA
Project Architects 2	Billy Young Architects 15 Graham Street JH4 SD6, Kent	Jay Barney Tel: 000000000 J.Barney@precosh.com	BYA
Project Architect 3	Sabato Architects 12 More street UG5 9YJ, Foren	John Kirk Tel: 000000000 J.Kirk@precosh.com	SA
Lead Principal Designer	Antonio Architects 5 Mansperger Street 3KL 5GH, Beverly	Tim Bloom Tel: 000000000 T.Bloom@precosh.com	AA
Sub Principal Designer 1	Spaysis Architects 20 Old Street HN2 8WH, Benson	Stanley Mauer Tel: 000000000 S.Mauer@precosh.com	SA
Sub Principal Designer 2	Billy Young Architects 15 Graham Street JH4 SD6, Kent	Jay Barney Tel: 000000000 J.Barney@precosh.com	BYA
Sub Principal Designer 3	Sabato Architects 12 More street UG5 9YJ, Foren	John Kirk Tel: 000000000 J.Kirk@precosh.com	SA
Principal Contractor	Justmoh 54 Cannon Street	Frank Graham Tel: 000000000 F.Graham@precosh.com	Justmoh

	9GH 5LM, Peterborough		
D&B Contractor	Justmoh 54 Cannon Street 9GH 5LM, Peterborough	Frank Graham Tel: 000000000 F.Graham@precosh.com	Justmoh
Facilities Manager	Payne Ltd 60 Red Street 4FG 3RT, Dikken	Benjamin Owusu Tel: 000000000 B.Owusu@precosh.com	PL
Landscape Architects	Haywood Architects 56 Bloom street 5JK MN, Glen	Kofi Oduro Tel: 000000000 K.Oduro@precosh.com	HA
Cost Consultants	EA Consult 74 Forever Street DF5 9TY, Kirk	Mary Borngreat Tel: 000000000 M.Borngreat@precosh.com	EA
Structural Engineer	Bernard Mason Kole 10 Mills street 6GK 8HO, Brandson	Jeffrey Stoy Tel: 000000000 J.Stoy@precosh.com	BMK
Services Engineer	Blair Mason 14 Mayflower street KL4 GF2, Beulah	Kojo Addo Tel: 000000000 K.Addo@precosh.com	BM
Fire Engineers	FE Ltd 70 Albion street HH1 VF4, Selby	Fred Forest Tel: 000000000 F.Forest@precosh.com	FEL
Façade Consultants	John Gray 52 Holy street TH5 WD6, Stone	Ted Moore Tel: 000000000 T.Moore@precosh.com	JG
Transport Consultants	Apak 47 Jack street KL2 NM5, Mayfair	Samuel Young Tel: 000000000 S.Young@precosh.com	Apak
Planning Consultants	Siedentop 41 Allmandring street GH2 FD5, Bonn	Stefan Fina Tel: 000000000 S.Fina@precosh.com	ST
Security Consultants	Engmann 48 Gray street QD4 AS5, Heibron	Jeremy Stove Tel: 000000000 J.Stove@precosh.com	EG
Sustainability Consultants	M. Friedrich 56 Frau street VB8 SF2, Bern	Kara Ross Tel: 000000000 K.Ross@precosh.com	MF

Access Consultants	Steiner 20 Gold street GV3 TY7, Clay	Vincent Ansong Tel: 000000000 V.Ansong@precosh.com	SN
Party Wall Surveyors	Mark Schneider 41 Horseley street JG1 UH, Bramford	Tay Shiller Tel: 000000000 T.Shiller@precosh.com	MS
Approved Inspector	Dreizler 89 Stanford street UJ1 FG2, Stoke	Jane Whyte Tel: 000000000 J.Whyte@precosh.com	DZ
Acoustic Consultants	Stewart Blair 87 Eagle road HH8 YU6, Earl	Malvin Owen Tel: 000000000 M.Owen@precosh.com	SB
Demolition Consultants/Enabling Works Contractors	Consar 62 Easy street PO5 ML5, Trent	Joseph Parker Tel: 000000000 J.Parker@precosh.com	Consar
Construction Contractors	Limex 90 Long road KL3 GJ8, Guilford	Gordon Brown Tel: 000000000 G.Brown@precosh.com	Limex
Legal Consultants	Kulendi & Partners 34 Stewart street GF1 VB2, Northampton	Millicent Bauer Tel: 000000000 M.Bauer@precosh.com	K&P
Archaeology Consultants	Sam Sey Ltd 41 Alter road BV2 CD7, Norman	Samuel Osei Tel: 000000000 S.Osei@precosh.com	SSL
Timber Specialists	S. Aryee Consult 56 Forest street KL2 YU6, Brent	Anas Pink Tel: 000000000 A.Pink@precosh.com	SAC
Fabric Specialists	SOS Ltd 90 Bay Street VC3 ET4, Shane	Gloria Powell Tel: 000000000 G.Powell@precosh.com	SOS
Geotechnical Specialists	Geotech Consult 77 Dowa street HJ1 GY4, Watford	Charles Hancock Tel: 000000000 C.Hancock@precosh.com	Geotech

Exhibit 8a: Site investigation and survey data tracker

Ref	Item	Action Owner/Notes	Status ● N/A
1	Ordnance Survey (Accuracy ± 400mm Urban Areas)		●
2	Historical Maps		●
3	Existing Record Drawings from Client		●
4	Drawings (List of Drawings or refer to a Schedule of Drawings)		●
5	Existing Health & Safety File (CDM) from Client (Buildings completed or altered since 1995)		N/A
6	Services/Utilities/Statutory Authorities (Location and Capacities) possible diversions and or need for new infrastructure e.g. sub-station. (Gas/water/electricity/ Sewers/Telephone/ Cables/ Drainage condition) Note: PAS 128:2014 Survey Type A		●
7	PTAL (Public Transport Accessibility Level) Rating		●
8	Other Town Planning Applications		
9	Asbestos (Demolition/ ground)		N/A
10	Aerial Photographs		N/A
11	Historic Photographs		N/A
12	Underground Features (Tunnel/Mining/Fracking)		
13	Boundaries / Land Ownership		●
14	Land Registry Plan		●
15	Ownership Deeds/Easements /Covenants		●
16	Rights of Way		●
17	Party Wall Matters		●
18	Rights of Light		
19	Listed Building – Historic England Listing Description		
20	Local Development Framework		●
21	Land Use Zones		●
22	Conservation Areas		●

Ref	Item	Action Owner/Notes	Status ● N/A
23	View Corridors to Landmarks		●
24	Height Restrictions		●
25	National Parks		●
26	Areas of Outstanding Natural Beauty (ANOB)		N/A
27	Green Belt		●
28	Refuse Collection Strategy		●
29	Sites of Special Scientific Interest (SSSI)		●
30	Local Byelaws		N/A
31	Topographic Survey - Measured Survey/Land Survey – Features		●
32	Laser Survey/ Sub scan Survey/ Cloud		N/A
33	Structural Survey / Condition Survey		●
34	Transport Survey		●
35	Parking Survey		●
36	Archaeology		●
37	Desktop Study/ Photographic survey/ Initial site visit report		N/A
38	Excavations/ Burial site survey		●
39	Noise/Acoustic Survey		●
40	Air Quality Survey		N/A
41	Arboriculture (Tree) Survey – Tree Preservation Orders/Clay Shrinkage/ Clay Heave/Root Protection Zones Note: BS 5837 (2012)		N/A
42	Ecological Survey (protected species/ bat roosts/snails/slow worms)		●
43	Environmental Assessment Survey		●
44	Flood Risk Assessment		●
45	Geotechnical Survey (bore holes/trial pits- existing features and foundations)		●
46	Contamination (Pathogens/Anthrax/ VOC's/Radon/Methane)		●

Status Key

- Information required/ awaiting.
- N/A Information not applicable.

Note - This survey tracker is for reference purposes only and should not be considered as a record of survey information or revisions. Responsibility sits with relevant consultants for advising the client of surveys required to carry out their design services and for keeping an up-to-date record of latest survey information.
* This list is not necessarily comprehensive

Exhibit 8b: Site investigation and survey data tracker

Ref	Item	Action Owner/Notes	Status ● N/A
47	Lead Paint Survey		●
48	Unexploded Ordnance (UXO) Report		●
49	Quality of incoming water		●
50	COMAH Regs 2015		●
51	*Other relevant Survey Information		●

Exhibit 9a: An excerpt of the Hazard Awareness and Risk Management Register (HARMR)

Project Name	Appolonia Project			Design Risk Tolerability/Acceptability
Project Number	40833			Design Risk tolerable
Prepared by	EA	Checked by	NA	Further consideration required- SFARP
Date	14/06/2018	Stage	4	Design Risk NOT tolerable

Risk Ref.	Relevant, Project Specific and Significant Hazard or Risk Identification	Design Control Measures proposed or adopted/ Residual Risk / Drg. Ref.	Design Risk Status / Owner	Date action required	Construction Design Risk Status / Owner
1.0	SITE - KEY CDM ISSUES & EXISTING SITE CONSTRAINTS				
1.1	Scheduled Ancient Monument (SAM) - Risk of archaeological finds <i>See CDM Analysis & Options Matrix</i>	Any unauthorized disturbance of the ground within a SAM constitutes a criminal offence. Ongoing liaison with MOLA and HE. <i>Refer to Historic Environment Assessment.</i>	MOLA/P&M	Before start on site	PC
1.2	Bay Street Conservation Area <i>See CDM Analysis & Options Matrix</i>	<i>Refer to Heritage Appraisal.</i>	KMHeritage/P&M		PC
1.3	Statutory listed buildings & road surfaces - Risk of damage <i>See CDM Analysis & Options Matrix</i>	The listed road surface of Lily flower Street must be protected and repaired or recorded, lifted and re-laid. Methodology has been developed and agreed with LBTH. <i>Refer to Heritage Appraisal.</i>	KMHeritage/P&M		PC
1.4	Locally listed buildings - Risk of damage <i>See CDM Analysis & Options Matrix</i>	<i>Refer to Heritage Appraisal.</i>	KMHeritage/P&M		PC
1.5	Risk of collapse during (partial) demolition of existing buildings and retention of façades <i>See CDM Analysis & Options Matrix</i>	Review phasing of construction works in relation to temporary works to retained structures. Demolition and façade retention strategy brief developed by BMK. PC and Temporary Works Designer	BMK	Enabling works CPs	PC
1.6	Exposure to asbestos/contaminants (All Plots)	Asbestos survey is required for all existing buildings and findings will be incorporated in the pre-construction information pack as well as in the tender pack. Identify extent of known asbestos/contaminants remaining post-demolition; identify any gaps and requirement for further testing/constraints. <i>Refer to Asbestos Survey Report.</i>	P&M		PC
1.7	Exposure to toxic materials in retained existing buildings, e.g. lead paint (All Plots)	Identify relevant retained elements & review safe methods for refurbishment works. Avoid dry sanding, drilling or cutting. Contractor should allow for surveys to be undertaken following completion of works to identify any residual hazards. Survey commissioned.	P&M		PC
1.8	Adjacent buildings - Party walls	All demolition works adjacent to retained wall/party wall to be carefully executed. Wall to be protected and its stability/integrity to be maintained during the works. Party wall awards are required with Network Rail. Goodman Broomhall act on behalf of the client and propose to enter into the awards shortly before start of works on site.	BMK/P&M		PC
1.9	Live Network Rail line to the north elevation of the site - Risk of falling onto tracks & electrocution by overhead lines <i>See CDM Analysis & Options Matrix</i>	The proximity of the development to the Network Rail asset requires a number of potential legal issues to be resolved, e.g. over sailing and access agreements for demolition, construction and building maintenance. Liaison with Network Rail ongoing.	BMK/P&M		PC

Exhibit 9b: An excerpt of the Hazard Awareness and Risk Management Register (HARMR)

Project Name	Appolonia Project			Design Risk Tolerability/Acceptability
Project Number	40833			Design Risk tolerable
Prepared by	EA	Checked by	NA	Further consideration required- SFARP
Date	14/06/2018	Stage	4	Design Risk NOT tolerable

Risk Ref.	Relevant, Project Specific and Significant Hazard or Risk Identification	Design Control Measures proposed or adopted/ Residual Risk / Drg. Ref.	Design Risk Status / Owner	Date action required	Construction Design Risk Status / Owner
1.10	Network Rail retaining wall - Protection at all stage of construction <i>See CDM Analysis & Options Matrix</i>	3m zone from the site boundary should be reserved for access to the retaining wall and for maintenance of proposed building facades. A response to Network Rail Draft planning condition has been issued. Ongoing liaison with Network Rail.	BMK/P&M		PC
1.11	Proximity of NBU underground tunnels - runs across the site from the south west corner to the north east <i>See CDM Analysis & Options Matrix</i>	AIP gained from NBUL. Monitoring regime in place with actionable trigger levels agreed. Surrounding ground movements are also being measured with extensometers to validate tunnel movements.	BMK		PC
1.12	Piling adjacent to NBU tunnels and Network Rail retaining wall <i>See CDM Analysis & Options Matrix</i>	Detail and extent of each pile type is subject to detailed ground investigation. Allow sufficient programme time depending on method. Note: Piling is outside NBUL exclusion zone. Ground movement assessment (GMA) is approved.	BMK		PC
1.13	Public sewers - Sewer diversion <i>See CDM Analysis & Options Matrix</i>	Condition surveys for connections to buildings are complete, level surveys outstanding. CCTV surveys for site drainage complete. Pre-condition surveys for Shoreditch High Street sewers complete where accessible. AIP has been gained for permanent works.	P&M		PC
1.14	Working adjacent to/on live services - Electrical/gas/water/foul drains/buried services <i>See CDM Analysis & Options Matrix</i>	All services survey information to be collated into a tracker document; identify gaps for surveys / exclusion zones.	P&M/Apak/BMK		PC
1.15	Existing UKPN substation relocation <i>See CDM Analysis & Options Matrix</i>	Key constraint and mitigation options are being considered to limit the potential effect on the functioning of the substation.	Apak/P&M		PC
1.16	Ground Obstructions: Remaining foundations and excavations of demolished buildings - presence of retaining walls and existing basements <i>See CDM Analysis & Options Matrix</i>	Construction Phase Plan to reference these issues in detail.	BMK		PC
1.17	Deep basement / land contamination (All Plots)	Desk top study carried out to identify historical site usage and whether there are any areas particularly susceptible to historical contamination. Test for types of waste product. The soil generally to be classified as hazardous. Contamination testing undertaken across site at Stage D Refresh to gain awareness of extent. <i>Refer to Ground Investigation Report.</i> Method statement to be provided by enabling works contractor.	BMK/Geotech		PC
1.18	Unexploded Ordnance (UXO) (All Plots) <i>See CDM Analysis & Options Matrix</i>	An UXO desk study has been carried out for the site by BACTEC. Study indicated the majority of the site is medium risk of containing unexploded ordnance with some areas considered a low risk.	P&M		PC

Exhibit 9c: An excerpt of the Hazard Awareness and Risk Management Register (HARMR)

Project Name	Appolonia Project			Design Risk Tolerability/Acceptability
Project Number	40833			Design Risk tolerable
Prepared by	EA	Checked by	NA	Further consideration required- SFARP
Date	14/06/2018	Stage	4	Design Risk NOT tolerable

Risk Ref.	Relevant, Project Specific and Significant Hazard or Risk Identification	Design Control Measures proposed or adopted/ Residual Risk / Drg. Ref.	Design Risk Status / Owner	Date action required	Construction Design Risk Status / Owner
		Follow proposal within UXO desk study report. <i>Explosive Ordinance Threat Assessment - 4 March 2014 Rev 1.</i> Strategy to be captured in enabling/main works contractor's CPs.			
1.19	Ground gas - Basement construction & other issues (All Plots)	Surveytronics have carried out an initial conceptual model based on their assessment of potential contaminated sources outlined in the Ground Investigation Report. Design has been coordinated through collaboration between specialists of various sectors and competent designers and is considered an appropriate design. But there is no written / formal approval from a specialist as of yet.	P&M/BMK		PC
1.20	Excessive noise, dust & vibration to occupied buildings	Noise, dust and vibration to be agreed with statutory authorities prior to construction. Ways of limiting the amount of dust to be developed before work begins. Avoid spraying harmful substances on site. GMB will facilitate the monitoring of movement, dust, vibration and noise measurements by negotiation and by means of the Award processes with Adjoining Owners and their surveyors.	GMB/P&M		PC
1.21	Surveys, reports and investigation	Structural and timber fabric surveys generally complete. CCTV surveys for site drainage complete. Surveys for limited outstanding areas being undertaken as access is made available. BMK will highlight where surveys have been taken so contractor is aware of where gaps exist. <i>Refer to M3 latest Survey Programme and Survey Tracker.</i>	P&M/BMK		PC
1.22	Fibre Optic Cables - Approvals to relocate	There are several providers with cables crossing the site, especially through Lily Flower Street. Both comms utility companies have requested fibre diversions. Follow-up meeting with team and Reach Active / Utilities to address concerns raised. Obtain AIP.	P&M/Apak		PC
1.23	Surrounding Highways - Basement excavations & façade retention <i>See CDM Analysis & Options Matrix</i>	The proposed works will require approval in principle from the respective highways department for the basement excavations and façade retention of 161 Pinoplex Street. Permanent works AIP gained with both Tower Hamlets and TfL. Contractor to develop temporary works approvals for 161 Commercial Street.	BMK		PC
1.24	Site access & establishment <i>See CDM Analysis & Options Matrix</i>	Method statements and strategy for site-wide construction traffic plan/safe pedestrian & vehicular routes/hoardings/protection/waste management developed by contractor.	P&M		PC

Exhibit 10: H&S File information framework

Content (Ref. CDM 2015 - L153 Appendix 4)	Notes / Comments /Action required	Completed
		Required
1. Brief description of work carried out	Antonio Architects to provide	
2. Any hazards that have not been eliminated	All	
3. Key structural principles	Structural Engineer to provide	
4. Hazardous material used	All	
5. Information regarding the removal or dismantling of installed plant and equipment	Services Engineer to provide	
6. Information about equipment provided for cleaning or maintaining the structure	All	
7. The nature, location and markings of significant services	Services Engineer to provide	
8. Information and as-built drawings of the building, its plant and equipment	Last Contract / Construction issue	
9. Project specific additional information	e.g. Fire Strategy information	

Exhibit 11: A sample of H&S file compilation template

Responsible party	Documentation / information required	Date/s requested	Date received	Date issued
<p>Architect / Principal Designer/ Principal Contractor</p> <p>Information to be provided by the Architect, Principal Designer or the Principal Contractor, for inclusion into the Health & Safety File, to allow subsequent designers to specify processes, which will not release the potential for harm held in the building fabric. This should, as a minimum, include information about the following:</p>	General Materials and finishes. Including any deviations from the generality and their locations.			
	Paints / Adhesives: General type, location and COSHH data sheets where relevant for future maintenance / removal.			
	Roof Assemblies: Materials and where applicable non-fragile life.			
	Glazing: Type, weight (and location where unusual).			
	Provisions for future maintenance, e.g. cleaning of glass, gutters, external painting, include assumptions about how it could be carried out. i.e. cherry picker or long pole.			
	Provisions for future dismantling. Including any deviations from the generality and their locations.			
	"Final Construction" "As built" drawings in .PDF and .DWG format			

Responsible party	Documentation / information required	Date/s requested	Date received	Date issued
Civil / Structural Designer Information to be provided by the Civil / Structural Engineer, for inclusion into the Health & Safety File, to allow subsequent designers to specify processes, which will not release the potential for harm held in the existing structure. This should, as a minimum, include information about the following:	The basic structural form, e.g. a pin-jointed steel frame with bracing.			
	The methods of structural analysis, including the names of any computer programmes used.			
	How the characteristic loads (occupancy and environmental, e.g. wind) were derived. List the British or European standards used.			
	The wind loads: basic wind speed used and a brief résumé of how the building was defined for calculating wind coefficients.			
	How the structural elements in the structure were designed. List all standards (with their date) that were used.			
	Any deviations from the requirements in the listed standards.			
	Critical components and how they work, e.g. fixing of pre-cast walling.			
	Requirements for and provisions for future maintenance, e.g. repainting steel, resurfacing roads, etc.			
	How the calculations may be obtained, e.g. file reference numbers, location.			
	How the building could be demolished or dismantled.			
"Final Construction"" As Built" drawings in .PDF and .DWG format				

Responsible party	Documentation / information required	Date/s requested	Date received	Date issued
<p>Mechanical and/or Refrigeration Designer / Engineer</p> <p>Information to be provided by the Building Services Designer(s) for inclusion into the Health & Safety File, to allow subsequent designers to minimise the risks associated with the work required to maintain / supplement existing services. This should include, as a minimum, information about the following:</p>	Design assumptions and parameters e.g. temperature, heat loss / gains, etc.			
	A schedule of significant Plant weights and / or sizes, their locations and special lifting requirements, e.g. lifts, cranes, hoists, etc.			
	Significant hazards associated with pieces of equipment, e.g. high pressures, high temperatures, and their locations, etc.			
	Schedule of the plant and equipment installed. (Note: Do not include manufacturers' catalogues or irrelevant information). Details to be included on the O&M Manual.			
	Provision for future inspections and maintenance and assumptions about how they would be carried out, e.g. from a 'cherry picker'.			
	How the services could be dismantled at the end of life.			
	Plan showing locations of incoming service isolation points.			
	"As Installed" drawings in .PDF and .DWG format			

Responsible party	Documentation / information required	Date/s requested	Date received	Date issued
Electrical Designer / Engineer Information to be provided by the Building Services Designer(s) for inclusion into the Health & Safety File, to allow subsequent designers to minimise the risks associated with the work required to maintain / supplement existing services. This should include, as a minimum, information about the following:	Design assumptions and parameters e.g. Illumination levels, etc.			
	A schedule of significant Plant weights and / or sizes, their locations and special lifting requirements.			
	Significant hazards associated with pieces of equipment, e.g. high voltages, high temperatures, and their locations, etc.			
	Schedule of the plant and equipment installed. (Note: Do not include manufacturers' catalogues or irrelevant information). Details to be included in the O&M Manual.			
	Provision for future inspections and maintenance and assumptions about how they would be carried out, e.g. from a 'cherry picker'.			
	How the services could be dismantled at the end of life.			
	Plan showing locations of incoming service isolation points.			
	"As Installed" drawings in .PDF and .DWG format			

Responsible party	Documentation / information required	Date/s requested	Date received	Date issued
<p>Landscape Architect / External Services Designer(s)</p> <p>Information to be provided by the Designer(s) of the External Services, for inclusion into the Health & Safety File, to help designers to minimise the risks associated with working on, or close to, existing services. This should, as a minimum, include information about the following:</p>	<p>The general form of the ground that the services were installed in, including any areas of significant hazard, e.g. made ground.</p>			
	<p>The location of services referenced from a fixed point on the building.</p>			
	<p>The location of isolation points within the building.</p>			
	<p>The depth of the services and utilities.</p>			
	<p>For drainage runs, the following additional information would be useful;</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • The falls of the drains; • The length, size and unit weight of the pipes; • The location of any drains, which carry highly hazardous waste from, e.g. pathology laboratories, petrol interceptors, etc; 			
	<p>A manhole schedule giving diameters, depths and form of access arrangements, e.g. mild steel ladders.</p>			
	<p>Provisions for future maintenance, e.g. Load bearing of hardstandings, lamp replacement to road lighting, etc.</p>			
<p>“As Installed” drawings in .PDF and .DWG format</p>				

Responsible party	Documentation / information required	Date/s requested	Date received	Date issued
Principal Contractor Information to be provided by the Principal Contractor for inclusion into the Health & Safety File, to help minimise the risks associated with working on, or close to, existing services. This should, as a minimum, include information about the following:	List of Subcontractors			
	List of Main Suppliers			
	O & M Manuals for Electrical, Mechanical, Refrigeration, Sprinklers, Lifts, etc. (Note: O&M Manuals to be kept as a separate document and cross referenced)			
	Product information from Nominated and Domestic Subcontractors / Suppliers relating to cleaning and maintenance of the structure, inc. COSHH data sheets where applicable.			
	Strategy for access, maintenance, cleaning, removal, renewal, de-commissioning, de-construction, demolition, etc.			
	Test Certificates / Guarantees and Warranties			
	Waste transfer documents / Air Clearance - Re-occupation Certification.			

Exhibit 12: An excerpt of design team meeting agenda

Design Team Protocol and Meeting Agenda (CDM specific items):-

1. CDM issues to be taken with all report/agenda items eg. Client, architect, structures, services, landscape, fire, etc. Not as a stand-alone subject.
2. All CDM Significant issues (risks and benefits) to be identified and captured in Schedule and CDM analysis report & drawings, with lead action owner and priority (RAG) indicated.
3. CDM Analysis Report items to form focus for meeting discussions
4. All CDM Significant issues to be prioritised and discussed by whole team in visual project context and resolution/mitigation/future action agreed and recorded.
5. Pre-Construction Information/ CDM Design Analysis report to be updated and issued, as project issues dictate, throughout the project, and at end of Work Stages.
6. Health and Safety File format and progress to be agreed from the start of the project.

Note: - All routine/normal/generic Contractor design & construction risks to be dealt with at Contractor Progress meetings.